

ECONOMY

MODELS OF BUDGET POLICY: SYSTEMATIZATION, FORMALIZED DESCRIPTION, AND GROUPING

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Abstract

The increase in frequency and depth of macrofinancial shocks significantly complicates the task of ensuring the stability of public finances, which makes it necessary to search for flexible models of budget revenue and expenditure management in conditions of economic turbulence. The purpose of the study is to systematize existing models of budget policy, provide a formalized description of them, and group them according to structural characteristics.

The article systematizes existing models of budget policy and formalizes them through a unified set of parameters covering the flexibility of revenue policy, the structure and priority of expenditures, the acceptability of the deficit, the role of debt financing, and the speed of budget adjustment.

Keywords: budget policy, fiscal adaptability, budget deficit, public debt, macrofinancial instability.

Problem statement. Deepening macrofinancial instability in the modern global economy is accompanied by growing uncertainty regarding budget revenue bases, increased expenditure pressure, and more complex debt management. Military conflicts, inflationary fluctuations, debt imbalances, and cyclical downturns create an environment in which the parameters of the budget system change faster than the institutional mechanisms for regulating them. Under such conditions, traditional approaches to revenue and expenditure management prove to be insufficiently sensitive to the nature of economic shocks.

Budget policy in conditions of instability involves simultaneous decision-making on revenue mobilization, determining expenditure priorities, an acceptable deficit level and methods of its financing. Each of these decisions affects other elements of the budget system. Changes in tax policy affect the size of the deficit; redistribution of expenditures affects borrowing needs; debt strategy limits the scope for economic stimulus. Thus, revenue and expenditure management takes on the character of a holistic system of interrelated parameters.

At the same time, there is no single approach to distinguishing between different models of such management in scientific and practical terms. Analysis tends to focus on individual instruments – countercyclicality, deficit constraints, or debt rules – without integrating them into comprehensive types of budget behavior. As a result, the concept of a “budget management model” remains methodologically vague: it is not clear which parameters are decisive for its identification and how their combination shapes different types of management decisions.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

The issue of managing revenues and expenditures of the state in conditions of macrofinancial turbulence is formed at the intersection of several scientific areas: fiscal policy theory, institutional architecture of the budget process, debt sustainability, and adaptation of public finances to crisis shocks. Contemporary literature shows that budget policy is no longer viewed as a

static system of resource allocation and is increasingly interpreted as a dynamic mechanism for responding to exogenous and endogenous macrofinancial challenges [1;2;3;4;5;6;7;8].

One of the key areas of research is the analysis of the cyclical behavior of fiscal policy in times of crisis. The work [4] states that during the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a significant change from traditional budget rules, indicating a transformation of budget response models. The scientific literature supports the thesis that fiscal behavior depends on the nature of the shock, which in fact points to the existence of different models of budget management.

This idea is further developed in the works devoted to local financial systems. The scientific work [7] indicates that territorial budgets respond to natural disasters through structural restructuring of revenues and expenditures, and the nature of the response depends on institutional capacity. This makes it possible to view the budget system as an adaptive structure, where changes occur not only quantitatively but also structurally.

A significant body of research is devoted to fiscal sustainability and debt dynamics. The institutional dimension of budget management is examined through the prism of fiscal governance. The work [1] shows that the existence of independent fiscal institutions affects the quality of the budget process and the timeliness of decision-making. Thus, institutional architecture determines not only formal rules but also the speed of budget adjustment.

The methodological aspect of classifying fiscal responses is presented in the work [6], using fuzzy-set QCA to identify combinations of factors that form different models of budget policy. This approach demonstrates that budget strategies are complex in nature and cannot be explained by a single parameter. A theoretical rethinking of the role of fiscal policy after crises is proposed in the work [5], which emphasizes the need to adapt budget rules to new macrofinancial realities.

Contemporary research by Ukrainian scientists focuses on the transformation of the budget system under

martial law. At the same time, international studies, in particular the work [2], emphasize the importance of structural modeling of the interaction between monetary and fiscal policy to achieve macroeconomic stability. The work [3] shows that the effectiveness of fiscal policy in countries with a transitional economy varies significantly depending on the initial macrofinancial conditions.

Thus, contemporary scientific literature examines: the dependence of budget policy on the type of macrofinancial shock, the decisive role of institutional architecture in shaping budget responses, the importance of structural characteristics (deficit, debt, expenditure flexibility), and the multifactorial nature of fiscal regimes. However, scientific research lacks a comprehensive formalized approach to systematizing existing models of management of revenue and expenditure of the state based on a unified set of parameters, followed by their grouping and establishing correspondence between types of budget management and types of macrofinancial instability. Most studies analyze individual aspects – fiscal sustainability, institutional reforms or responses to specific crises – without integrating them into a single structured model.

Despite the significant amount of research in the field of fiscal policy and budget adaptation to crises, the problem of parametric clustering of models for managing revenues and expenditures of the state remains insufficiently developed, which necessitates further scientific research in this area.

The purpose of the article. The purpose of the study is to systematize existing models of budget policy, provide a formalized description of them, and group them according to structural characteristics.

Presentation of the main material. Analysis of scientific approaches and practices of budget policy in conditions of macrofinancial instability makes it possible to identify five models of revenue and expenditure management: the fiscally restrained, the stimulating, the debt-active, the mobilizing, and the adaptively balanced. They differ in terms of the logic of revenue mobilization, the structure of budget priorities, the regime of deficit and debt financing, as well as the intensity and speed of budget adjustments in response to shocks. The fiscally restrained model is based on minimizing the deficit and limiting the debt burden; tax policy is focused on stability and predictability, and the expenditure structure is characterized by a high share of social commitments and low flexibility of redistribution. The stimulating model involves a temporary expansion of the deficit to support economic activity, with an emphasis on the investment and capital component of expenditures and more flexible use of tax instruments.

The debt-active model is based on the systematic use of borrowing as a key financing resource, which determines the persistent deficit and dependence of the budget structure on the availability of debt sources. The mobilizing model is implemented in conditions of high turbulence and involves the centralization of resources, prioritization of security and defense expenditures, and active use of temporary fiscal measures. The adaptively balanced model combines elements of restraint and stimulation: the deficit is kept within controlled limits, the expenditure structure is adjusted depending on macrofinancial conditions, and debt is stabilized in the medium term. Comparative characteristics of the models are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Comparative characteristics of revenue and expenditure management models

Parameter	Model				
	The fiscally restrained	The stimulating	The debt-active	The mobilizing	The adaptively balanced
Deficit regime	Minimization	Temporary extension	Systemic deficit	Controlled	Flexible regulation
Debt policy	Restrictions	Growth in the stimulation phase	Active involvement	Control	Stabilization
Tax strategy	Rate stability	Flexible changes	Reliance on borrowing	Temporary measures	Combined approach
Expenditure structure	High proportion of liabilities	Investment priority	Dependence on financing	Safety priority	Balance between directions
Budget flexibility	Low	Average	High	Centralized	Adaptive

In practice, managing revenues and expenditures of the state in conditions of macrofinancial instability is implemented as a combination of interrelated decisions on resource mobilization, the structure of budget priorities, the acceptable level of the deficit, and debt financing instruments. Accordingly, it is advisable to record differences between budget management models not based on a single indicator (e.g., deficit or debt), but as a comprehensive management configuration that includes revenue, expenditure, debt, and adaptation components simultaneously.

To formalize such configurations, a “passport” approach can be used (each management model will be described by a single set of standardized characteristics grouped into blocks (revenue, expenditure, deficit/debt, adjustments)). Each feature will be coded according to an ordinal scale of intensity of manifestation. The agreed set of features and codes that make up the “passport” of the model will be provided.

In further research, the matrix of coded features can be used as an input base for cluster grouping of models. Since each model is described by the same set of parameters, it can be interpreted as a vector of values

in a multidimensional space of features. This makes it possible to move from qualitative typology to formalized grouping of models according to their degree of structural similarity.

Conclusion. Approaches to budget management were systematized, and five models of revenue and expenditure management were identified, differing in terms of the acceptable deficit level, the role of borrowing, the flexibility of expenditure, and the speed of budget adjustment. To enable a formal comparison of the models, it is possible to describe them parametrically using a unified set of characteristics covering revenue policy, expenditure priorities, deficit regime, and debt financing.

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